

UDC: 336.748.12:004.738.5

Review of Bitcoin Price Fluctuation Over the Last Six Months and Analysis of Support, Resistance Levels, and Trading Volume Concentrations Zones

Vitalii Viter

Master of financial and economic security

DSAEU

viterfirs@gmail.com

Introduction

In recent years, the cryptocurrency market has been attracting increasing attention from both institutional investors and private trades. Among all digital assets, Bitcoin (BTC) plays the role of a benchmark instruments, shaping the trends of the rest of the market. Given Bitcoin's high volatility, analysing price fluctuations, buying and selling zones, as well volume concentrations levels, is crucial for assessing market trends.

The aim of this paper is to analyse Bitcoin price fluctuations over the last six months, identify key technical levels, support and resistance zones, as well as buying and selling activity volumes based on publicly available exchange data.

Keywords: Bitcoin, technical analysis, resistance levels, support zones, trading volume, cryptocurrency market, volume profile, market phases, buying zone, cryptocurrency analytics.

Review of Materials and Sources

The research utilized data from open sources, including:

- Exchanges such as Binance and Bybit (data on volumes, prices, open interest);
- Aggregators like TradingView (historical charts, indicators).

The study covers the period from October 2024 to March 2025 inclusive. The main focus is on medium-term price movements, reactions to key levels, and cluster volume analysis.

Analysis of Bitcoin Price Dynamics and Volume Activity Zones (October 2024 – April 2025)

Over the past six months, the Bitcoin market has exhibited three clearly defined price movement phases: a growth phase, a distribution phase followed by decline, and the current consolidation phase. Each of these phases was characterized by changes in market structure, trading volume, and support and resistance levels. The analysis was conducted using daily candlestick charts of the BTC/USDT pair on the Binance exchange, with the application of the Volume Profile indicator, which made it possible to identify zones of concentrated trading activity. The following review will be based on Figure 1.

During the period from October to December 2024, a stable growth phase took place. The BTC price moved within an ascending channel, surpassing the key psychological level of \$40 000. This upward movement was accompanied by a moderate increase in volume, indicating a gradual accumulation of positions. The main accumulation zone during this period can be considered the price range \$52 000 – \$60 000, where a high density of buy-side trades was recorded.

Figure 1. Bitcoin price chart on a 1-day timeframe

Since the beginning of January 2025, the market has entered a distribution phase. Several attempts were made to break through the \$89 000 - \$91 000 level, but they were not supported by sufficient volume. This indicates the presence of a strong resistance level where

investors were taking profits. As a result, the price gradually declined to the support zone around \$74 000, marking the beginning of a new market phase – consolidation.

From March to April 2025, the market has shown signs of sideways movement withing the \$76 000 - \$86 000 range. During this phase, a high-liquidity zone formed around the \$80 000 - \$82 000 level, according to the volume profile. This is where the profile. This is where the Point of Control (PoC) is observed – the price level with the highest concentration of trades during the analysed period. This indicates intense competition between buyers and sellers and suggest that this range may serve as a future price impulse.

As of April 15, 2025, Bitcoin is trading near the \$85 880 mark. The price is approaching a local resistance level (\$86 000 - \$87 000), and a breakout above this zone could trigger a new wave of growth toward the previous highs in the \$89 000 - \$91 000 range.

In case of a rejection from this level, a return to the support zone of \$74 000 - \$76 000 is likely – a range that previously served as volume accumulation area.

Analysis of resistance levels, selling zones, and volume concentration on March – April 2025

Between early March and mid-April 2025, a clear consolidation zone formed in the Bitcoin market within the price range of \$74 000 - \$86 000. After a sharp decline in February, the price stabilized withing this zone, accompanied by increasing trading volumes at lower levels. This indicates a shift in market dynamics – from a sell-off phase to accumulation. The following review will be based on Figure 2.

The updated charts shows that the highest concentration of trading volume is located at the \$82 000 - \$82 500 level. This confirms the presence of a local balance zone between buyers and sellers. This price cluster serves as a medium-term resistance level, and breakout above it may signal a transition into a growth phase. At the same time, the lover boundary - \$74 000 - \$75 000 forms a clear support zone, where increased buyer activity was observed during the price drop in mid-March. Special attention should be paid to the \$89 000 level, which is marked on the chart as a strong resistance zone. In the past, it served as a key selling level, where significant positions occurred following a local high. Although the price has not yet reached this level again, there is strong confirmation of its relevance, as it aligns with the previous distribution zone and peak volume levels recorded in February.

As of April 15, 2025, the BTC/USDT price stands at \$85 650, placing in it close proximity to the upper boundary of the short-term trading range. Combined with the high volume accumulated in the \$81 000 - \$83 000 range, this confirms the importance of highlighting the \$86 000 - \$89 000 resistance zone as a potential reversal area or a breakout level – should the positive momentum continue.

Thus, technical analysis and the volume profile confirm presence of strategic levels that determine market behaviour in the near future. Taking these into account allows for the development pf well-founded forecast regarding potential scenarios for further price movement.

Figure 2. Bitcoin price chart on the 1-day time frame with a focus on March and April.

Conclusion

The conducted analysis has revealed the key stages of Bitcoin's market behaviour over the past six months, which included phases of growth, distribution, and consolidation. Each of these phases was marked by changes in price structure, trading volumes, and the market's response to support and resistance level. A detailed review of the price dynamics made it

possible to identify strategically important zones where accumulation or distribution of the asset occurred. Practical attention should be given to the \$81 000 - \$83 000 range, which recorded the highest trading volume over the past month. This range can be considered the current level of marked equilibrium. The price's decline to the \$74 000 - \$75 000 support zone and its subsequent rebound confirms strong buyer activity at lower levels. At the same time, the \$89 000 - \$90 000 levels serves as a strong resistance zone, which previously acted as a barrier to further upward movement.

Based on the analysis of the volume profile, price behaviour, and local market structures, it can be concluded that Bitcoin's further dynamics will largely depend on whether the price can break through the \$86 000 - \$89 000 resistance zone. A successful breakout could potentially pave the way for a retest of local highs, while a failed attempt may lead to another corrective phase within the current trading range.

References

1. Binance. (2025). *Bitcoin price chart*. Binance. <https://www.binance.com/en/price/bitcoin>
2. Buffett, W. (2006). *The intelligent investor* (Rev. ed.). HarperBusiness.
3. Choithani, Tamanna, et al. "A comprehensive study of artificial intelligence and cybersecurity on bitcoin, crypto currency and banking system." *Annals of Data Science* 11.1 (2024): 103-135.
4. Mokni, Khaled, et al. "On the efficiency and its drivers in the cryptocurrency market: the case of Bitcoin and Ethereum." *Financial Innovation* 10.1 (2024): 39.
5. Ranaldo, Angelo, Ganesh Viswanath-Natraj, and Junxuan Wang. "Blockchain currency markets." *Swiss Finance Institute Research Paper* 24-29 (2024).
6. TradingView. A platform for technical analysis of financial markets. URL: <https://www.tradingview.com> (дата звернення: 15.04.2025).
7. Viter, Vitalii Andriiovych. "Improving the Process of Protecting the Financial and Economic Security of an Enterprise from Fraud Risks." (2024).